

ID	Heuristic	Severity scores	Avg	Max	Is Priority?
H1	Visibility of System Status	1, 2, 0, 3	1.5	3	Yes
H2	Match Between System and Real World	0, 2, —, 3	1.67	3	Yes
H3	User Control and Freedom	0, 2, —, 2	1.33	2	Yes
H4	Consistency and Standards	0, 1, —, 0	0.33	1	No
H5	Error Prevention	1, 2, 0, 3	1.5	3	Yes
H6	Recognition Rather Than Recall	0, 2, —, 0	0.67	2	No
H7	Flexibility and Efficiency of Use	1, 0, —, 1	0.67	1	No
H8	Aesthetic and Minimalistic Design	0, 0, —, 0	0	0	No
H9	Help Users Recognize, Diagnose & Recover	0, 2, —, 2	1.33	2	Yes
H10	Help and Documentation	1, 3, 2, 2	2	3	Yes